

FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE PEOPLE'S REPUBLIC OF CHINA

Sodikova F.J.

Student of Tashkent institute of chemical-technology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880816>

Abstract. *This article examines foreign economic relations with China, one of the largest partners of Uzbekistan, their statistics for the last 5 years, main exports and imported products, the Project "One Belt, One Road" and the amount of investments in our country.*

Keywords: *trade corridor, "One Belt, One Road", "green" corridor, Export, import, economic shock, degree of dependence, PRC investment, Foreign Trade Communication.*

INTRODUCTION

As every country wants to improve and develop its economic aspect, it should be in constant contact with foreign countries. This not only increases the potential of the domestic market in the country, but also opens the way to enter the world market and develop other areas. Therefore, Uzbekistan is constantly trying to conquer new markets, increase the volume of external communication and attract foreign investors to our country. As one of such efforts, the relationship with the People's Republic of China, which is increasing year by year and beneficial for both sides, can be cited as a clear example.

DISCUSSION

Economy occupies a central place in the relations between Central Asian countries and China. Central Asian countries mainly export resource goods, while China supplies more high-value-added products.

For several centuries, the Great Silk Road played an important role as an international trade corridor. Today, this direction has become the only "One Belt, One Road" project in Asia, which builds a new architecture of relations that strives to unite countries based on mutual interest and consideration of each other's interests.

In addition, the countries intend to intensify efforts to develop the "green" corridor in order to ensure continuous transportation of goods, further optimize the structure of mutual trade, strengthen cooperation in the field of natural gas production and renewable energy sources.

Our country has long-standing foreign economic relations with the People's Republic of China. According to the data of foreign economic activity of the Statistical Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 2023, China became the main trading partner of Uzbekistan. During the year, the volume of trade between the two countries increased by 52.2% and amounted to 13.7 billion US dollars. Uzbekistan has the largest share of 20.9% of imports and 13% of exports. The volume of capital investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023 will be 352.1 trillion. if it was soum, 25.6% of it corresponds to China's share.

In the graph below, we can see the changes of export and import over the last 5 years:

It is known from the graph that in the last 5 years, the import and export of Uzbekistan has grown in a general sense. In particular, our imports have almost doubled. As a reason for this, we can say that the economic and political relations between Uzbekistan and China are improving, the impact of the post-pandemic economic shock on Chinese economy is decreasing, and the economic potential of Uzbekistan is developing. Looking at the numbers, the amount of import in

2020 was 4501.3 million US dollars, and compared to this period, an increase of 109.4% in 2021, 142.3% in 2022 and 250.2% in 2023 was observed. The main part of imported products is cars, oil and gas and copper.

Graph 1

As can be seen from the graph, the highest figure is recorded in 2023, and the main part of imported products is cars, oil, copper, rubber, metal and metal products.

But when it comes to exports, the trend changed between 1,900-2,519 billion US dollars, and by the end of the period, this figure decreased, that is, from 2,519 million US dollars in 2019 to 2,461.8 million US dollars in 2023. Exported products in 2023 are mainly resource goods such as fruits and vegetables, mineral fuel, oil and its processing products, cotton, thread, copper and plastic products.

Graph 2

In general, the total volume of bilateral trade in 2019-2023 is at least 6,432.2 million US dollars (2020) and at most 13,721.9 million US dollars (2023). The average growth compared to 2023 was equal to 1.68 times.

China, which is considered one of our major partners in foreign trade relations, occupies high positions in several fields, which in turn indicates that the level of dependence of Uzbekistan on China is increasing. Investment cooperation is also being actively implemented. Over the past 10 years, the People's Republic of China has invested more than \$10 billion in the economy of Uzbekistan, in particular, in oil and gas, chemical, building materials production, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, light industry and many other sectors. Also, the investment in the economy of Uzbekistan has increased 5 times in recent years. As of December 1, 2023, 13,353 enterprises were established as a result of PRC investment, which is a 3-fold increase compared to previous years.

Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev paid a state visit to this country on January 23-24 at the invitation of the Chairman of the People's Republic of China Xi Jinping. In accordance with the program of the visit, high-level talks and a number of bilateral meetings were held in Beijing. The following were signed in the presence of the leaders:

- Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the People's Republic of China on cooperation in the field of environmental protection;
- Agreement on technical and economic cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the People's Republic of China;
- Agreement on cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the People's Republic of China on the development of human resources;
- Agreement between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the People's Republic of China on the cooperation of state research institutions;
- Agreement between the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Education of the People's Republic of China on cooperation in the field of Chinese language teaching;
- Protocol between the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the General Administration of Customs of the People's Republic of China on phytosanitary requirements and control in the export of peas from Uzbekistan to China;
- Protocol on deepening cooperation between the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State Committee for Reforms and Development of the People's Republic of China on the China-Central Asia-Europe railway expressway;
- Protocol on the development of cooperation in the field of new electric vehicles between the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Commerce of the People's Republic of China;
- Memorandum of agreement between the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Affairs of the People's Republic of China on cooperation in the field of poverty reduction;
- Memorandum of cooperation between the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Science and Technology of the People's Republic of China on further strengthening of scientific and technical cooperation;
- Protocol on cooperation in the field of standardization between the Technical Regulatory Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Standardization Administration of the People's Republic of China;

- Agreement between the Ministry of Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Civil Aviation Administration of China on the joint establishment of the "Air Silk Road";
- Cooperation plan in the field of tourism between the Tourism Committee under the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of the People's Republic of China in 2024-2026;
- Agreement on establishment of partnership relations between Tashkent region and Shaanxi province;
- Agreement on the establishment of partnership relations between the cities of Samarkand and Sindaio, etc.

SUMMARY

Analyzing the visit of the President of Uzbekistan to China, it can be said that the state visit to China was very successful and effective in terms of strengthening economic cooperation between the countries of the region in today's difficult geo-economic conditions.

Central Asian countries mainly export resource goods, while China supplies more high-value-added products. At the same time, there is a significant imbalance in bilateral trade. The share of Central Asian countries in China's foreign trade is only 1.1 percent. China is the main economic partner for the countries of the region. For example, China accounts for 34% of total foreign trade in Kyrgyzstan, and 18% in Kazakhstan.

In general, the new initiatives put forward by our President are serving the closer integration of the Central Asian countries into world economic relations, meanwhile, the world is observing the trends of their decay and disintegration.

REFERENCES

1. <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/6345>
2. <https://stat.uz/uz/default/press-relizlar/34336-2023-3>
3. <https://stat.uz/uz/default/press-relizlar/17505-2022>
4. <https://stat.uz/uz/default/press-relizlar/7658-2021-yil>
5. <https://stat.uz/uz/default/press-relizlar/5674-2020-yil>
6. <https://stat.uz/uz/default/press-relizlar/5675-2019-yil>